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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

This collection comprises a series of cross-national public opinion surveys conducted by the Pew Research Center between 2003 and 2019 as part of its Global Attitudes and Trends project, alongside one thematically distinct survey, the International Science Survey, fielded in 2019. The overall survey design is stable, but questionnaire content evolves from year to year: individual waves often emphasize particular issues, such as international conflict, global leadership, economic anxiety, or regional political developments.

The review covers multiple datasets available via the below links:

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/international-science-survey/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2019-survey-data/> (includes Lithuania, Russia, Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2018-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2017-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2015-survey-data/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/2014-spring-global-attitudes/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2013-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2012-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2011-survey/> (includes Lithuania, Russia, Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2010-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/fall-2009-survey-data/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2009-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2008-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2007-survey-data/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2006-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/may-2005-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/march-2004-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/may-2003-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/march-2003-survey-data/> (includes Russia)

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Review of Pew’s Global Attitudes and International Science Surveys (2003–2019)

by Stas Gorelik

This collection comprises a series of cross-national public opinion surveys conducted by the Pew Research Center between 2003 and 2019 as part of its Global Attitudes and Trends project, alongside one thematically distinct survey, the International Science Survey, fielded in 2019. Pew relied on multistage probability sampling designs within each country, with typical sample sizes ranging from approximately 800 to 1,500 respondents. Fieldwork was implemented by local survey organizations under Pew’s supervision. As for the post-Soviet states and Baltics—Lithuania, Russia, Ukraine—included in these surveys, face-to-face interviewing remains the dominant mode throughout the entire period.

The overall survey design is stable, but questionnaire content evolves from year to year: individual waves often emphasize particular issues, such as international conflict, global leadership, economic anxiety, or regional political developments, rather than reproducing a fixed core instrument. Fieldwork timing differs across surveys and, in some cases, coincides with major political or economic events.

The International Science Survey, conducted in 2019, follows the same general methodological model as the Global Attitudes surveys (national probability samples and face-to-face interviews) but employs a distinct questionnaire focused specifically on public views of science and technology. Its substantive emphasis includes trust in scientists, perceptions of scientific progress, views on the social and moral implications of new technologies.

Despite substantial variation in questionnaire content, the surveys exhibit partial thematic continuity across waves. Most include some combination of evaluations of national conditions, views on political leadership or governance, and attitudes toward major international actors, including Russia. Economic perceptions, such as assessments of national economic performance or living standards, appear frequently but not universally. Note, however, that no single set of questions is repeated identically across all surveys.

Coverage of post-Soviet countries and Baltic region within this collection is selective but recurring. Russia is included in all nineteen surveys listed here. Ukraine appears in six waves (2007, Fall 2009, 2011, 2014, 2015, and 2019), typically in surveys with a stronger focus on European politics or international affairs. Lithuania is included twice (2011 and 2019), representing the Baltic region.

Data access: Links to the datasets are listed below; to download them, an account with Pew Research Center must be created.

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/international-science-survey/> (includes Russia)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2019-survey-data/> (includes Lithuania, Russia, Ukraine)

<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2018-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2017-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2015-survey-data/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/2014-spring-global-attitudes/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2013-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2012-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2011-survey/> (includes Lithuania, Russia, Ukraine)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2010-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/fall-2009-survey-data/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2009-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
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<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2007-survey-data/> (includes Russia and Ukraine)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/spring-2006-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/may-2005-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
<https://www.pewresearch.org/dataset/march-2004-survey-data/> (includes Russia)
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